

Influence of seedling rate on tungro (RTV) incidence at Cuttack

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A trial under protected and unprotected conditions measured influence of number of seedlings per hill on RTV incidence. Protection was 0.01% decamethrin sprayed weekly up to heading. TN1 (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant) were planted in 3- × 3-m plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Ten days after transplanting (DT), infected Jaya tillers were transplanted around each plot to inoculate unprotected plots. Protected plots were not inoculated. Disease incidence was recorded 60 DT.

Disease incidence in TN1 was 100% in all unprotected plots; it varied in

Effect of number of seedlings per hill on RTV incidence and grain yield in rice cultivars TN1 and Ratna.^a Orissa, India.

Seedlings/hill (no.)	Disease incidence (%) in unprotected plots		Grain yield (t/ha)			
			Unprotected		Protected	
	TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna
1	100	62 d	0.5 a	1.8 c	1.5 b	2.8 b
2	100	42 c	0.5 a	2.3 bc	2.1 a	3.4 ab
3	100	28 b	0.5 a	2.5b	2.1 a	3.4 ab
4	100	12 a	0.5 a	3.1 a	2.0 a	3.6 ab
6	100	13 a	0.6 a	3.1 a	2.2 a	3.6 ab
8	100	9 a	0.6 a	3.1 a	2.0 a	3.8 a

^a In each column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at P = 0.05 by DMRT.

tolerant cultivar Ratna (see table). Disease incidence gradually decreased with seedling rate.

Grain yield differed between protected and unprotected plots. Yields of TN1 were higher under protected conditions. Under protected conditions, yields did not significantly differ at 2 to 5 seedlings/hill, but were lower for 1 seedling/hill. Yields of

Ratna under unprotected conditions gradually increased with numbers of seedlings/hill; there was no significant yield difference among 4, 6, and 8 seedlings/hill.

Number of seedlings per hill had no effect on susceptible TN1, especially under unprotected conditions. Four seedlings per hill is optimum for Ratna. □

Growth and virulence of two isolates of *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot (ShR) in rice

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ShR is caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* and *S. artenuatum*, the former being more prevalent. To obtain information on the variation in growth and virulence of *S. oryzae*, two isolates that differed in colony color were used. The mycelium of isolate 283-P was slightly pinkish, isolate 1183-W appeared whitish on potato dextrose agar medium. Three areas were studied: morphology of the conidia and conidiophores, growth of the two isolates in three semisolid and liquid media, and virulence of the isolates in different rice genotypes.

No difference in morphology was found. Growth in Czapek's solution agar (CZA), malt yeast extract agar (MYA), and potato dextrose agar (PDA) were similar, but isolate

Linear growth of 2 isolates of *Sarocladium oryzae* in 3 media at 28 ± 2 °C.